

A review on Applications of BIM Technology in Road, Bridge and Tunnel Safety Construction Management

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Abstract- Strict engineering quality and safety management, to some extent, is to help promote the long-term development of highway and bridge technology, while also effectively guaranteeing the overall safety of bridge and highway construction projects and reducing the occurrence of safety accidents. BIM technology is extensively employed in various industries due to the rapid growth of science and technology. The use of BIM technology in road and bridge construction management can provide a solid foundation for decision-making throughout the road and bridge construction process, improve the level of road and bridge construction management, and ensure the quality and service life of road construction. Furthermore, the use of BIM technology may not only expedite the building duration but also reduce the cost of roads and bridges. A novel style of municipal engineering design and construction is the urban subterranean utility tube. By using BIM technology, the building information modeling (BIM) techniques for managing the construction of railway tunnels, including naming conventions for structuralized components and modeling precision criteria, are investigated. In this study, the application of BIM technology in highway and bridge safety management is examined in order to effectively enhance the quality and efficiency of construction safety management measures, therefore providing an essential reference value for bridge construction management safety. This paper shows the benefits of BIM software in the construction of a municipal tunnel by utilizing its collaborative design, comprehensive pipeline design, construction schedule, and process simulation functions. And also this paper discuss, the procedures and benefits of a 3D model of a visualized design for a railway tunnel. The processes for calculating and refining a 4D model of a railway tunnel's construction are investigated.

Keywords: BIM, Construction Safety Management, Implementation, problems, RBT(Road, Bridge and Tunnel)

1. Introduction

At the moment, the domestic economic development trend is positive, per capita automobile ownership is increasing, and the need for roads and bridges is increasing. In this setting, modern road and bridge building has become increasingly complicated, influenced not only by the physical environment, but also by a variety of professional technology. The majority of contemporary road and bridge projects are still in the two-dimensional engineering drawing stage. And, with this inefficient mode of information transfer, it is difficult to identify flaws in the project for the first time, which not only impedes building progress but also degrades the overall appearance of the project. In this context, the use of BIM technology is required to enable effective administration and control of road and bridge projects.

To strengthen the core competency of construction and engineering firms, we must continually improve management while employing existing management methods and implementing sophisticated BIM technology to focus on safety management during highway and bridge building. The use of scientifically sound BIM technology in bridge construction safety management can help to establish a framework of safety management models compatible with highway construction, which can help to improve construction quality while also promoting industrial development.

With the rapid expansion of urbanization, it has been a trend in urban development to utilize utility tunnels to lay municipal pipes, which is a structure and auxiliary facilities that can handle a range of pipelines and equipment in subterranean space . By boosting utility tunnel construction, we may eliminate concerns like construction damage to subsurface pipes and enhance the usage rate of underground space.

However, because of the unique nature of the utility tunnel project, it has significant construction problems, high input prices, multiple specializations, challenging geological conditions, and high safety and reliability requirements. Furthermore, during the subterranean building process, there may be a collision with the municipal pipeline that has already been created, and it may also include various complications such as the development of a subway project.

The majority of relevant utility tunnel research, both at home and abroad, focuses on project design .For example, Zong et al., used specific engineering design to incorporate into a comprehensive high-tech industrial zone in

Qingdao, where the municipal pipelines in the utility tunnel were thoroughly analysed, and the combination of utility tunnel and direct burial was finally determined. Wang et al., performed a crucial analysis on the drainage system, ventilation, and fire protection of the utility tunnel. Cong investigated the source of the fire and the fire condition in the extensive pipe trench surrounding the CDC in Guangzhou. As a result, the utility tunnel's fire prevention system was constructed. Furthermore, several academics created the auxiliary structure of the underground utility tunnel project, as well as the financing and advantages. In recent years, some progress has been achieved in the urban underground pipe network informatization and BIM-based utility tunnel development. Such as Zhang et al., implemented GIS technology in the management of a water supply pipe network in Xi'an and obtained the benefits. Park et al., developed an engineering system integrating BIM and GIS to estimate the cost of the project in order to choose the best route and further improve the project construction method. Three-dimensional visualization of pipe network water pressure by integrating plane labelling, two-dimensional colouring, and three-dimensional solid map provided scientific basis for the optimal dispatching and construction planning of water supply network. To achieve real-time monitoring of subterranean pipes, some international researchers have advocated the establishment of automated alarm, environmental monitoring, structural monitoring, video surveillance, and other management systems. Additionally, several studies have suggested a plan for managing subterranean pipelines based on visualization technologies and adapted it to urban utility tunnels.

1.2. BIM concept

BIM is a 3D digital technology-based building information model. Simultaneously, in order to build a database, it is essential to gather and consolidate numerous pieces of data. BIM models employ digital techniques to interface with design units and project-specific functionality. BIM technology is now widely employed in a variety of construction projects.

1.3. Importance of BIM Technology

An important stage is to create a BIM model based on static road models and building processes (including significant project structures). The design plan of the project is included, its dynamic model is constructed, and the full road operation process is presented to mimic the operational condition based on the construction of the time dimension. Construction safety management is an essential aspect of the highway and bridge construction management content and plays a greater role in assisting the attainment of the project's operational objectives. It is commonly understood that, given the current environment, operators must enhance their usage of BIM technology. Effective use of technology to improve overall bridge project management and boost the efficiency of structural safety management in order to more effectively assure road bridge safety.

2. Applications of BIM Technology in Road, Bridge and Tunnel Construction Management

2.1. Pre-construction BIM application of Road and Bridge projects

To construct road and bridge projects based on 3D models, visualization techniques were used for collision inspections and depth design. As a result of the intricacy of road and bridge construction, detecting potential pipeline collisions is difficult. A building information model associates each component with parameter-driven information. To remedy mistakes and save time, the 3D model is collision-checked, automatically displaying the amount of collisions, producing precise drawings of collision spots, and sending collision detection reports. In addition to the components, BIM can detect collisions during construction between machines, workstations, machines, and structures. BIM also offers traffic flow analysis, analyses performance metrics such as structural stability and load-bearing capacity, and can execute complete and partial refining procedures in real time. All of this contributes to save construction costs, lower construction risks, and assure building quality. Temporary construction facilities such as material storage yards and steel fabrication plants are readily concentrated in small construction zones and become more crowded when meeting adverse terrain due to the long highways utilized to construct road and bridge projects. To identify the relative placements of roads, key bridges, platforms, trestles, big machinery, and material processing facilities, use BIM technology to model the measured 3D topography and integrate it with the overall layout of the construction area. To create a 3D visual blueprint of the building site.

2.2. Application of BIM in Road and Bridge project construction

At every level of the building process, BIM offers precise management, 3D visualization, 4D time, and 5D cost. BIM models incorporate important data including quantities, timetables, and budgets together with the related contracts, drawings, and supplies. Simulate construction after synthesis and provide safety and other information. Using digital management, real-time monitoring, and other methods to simulate project progress, material consumption, etc., in order to provide reasonable and accurate data for key construction nodes, business operations, planning, and other aspects of the construction, saving time and money, and improving construction management efficiency. The majority of domestic highway and bridge projects today utilize Gantt charts to schedule numbers and text. Highway and bridge projects have a distinctive structural form where quality, cost, safety, materials, etc. are typically regulated according to the construction schedule.

2.3. Post construction BIM Application for Road and Bridge projects

Emergency management for finished components that may be exposed to threats like fractures, collapses, and landslides is very demanding for road and bridge projects, as distinct elements of the road are created in a precise sequence throughout construction. Real-time access is possible to spatially specific data that is saved in BIM. A BIM system can offer particular information while emergency workers are in route and assist in locating and continuously identifying possible risks and other crises in the case of a disaster. In addition to aiding in issue solving, it increases the operations and maintenance staff's preparedness for emergency circumstances. Building information models may also evaluate disaster losses to recreate disasters, create logical fixes, and research and test their reaction strategies.

2.4. Road and Bridge Construction Safety Management

Road and bridge building necessitates a large amount of people, material, and financial resources, and there are some potential safety issues. Safety management on the building site must be reinforced to avoid the incidence of safety mishaps. BIM technology can simulate the construction process and construction links, identify potential safety hazards on site in real time, re-examine the construction plan through detailed simulation, understand the unsafe factors on the construction site, and take preventive measures in advance to eliminate potential safety hazards and accidents at the source.

BIM technology, on the other hand, can accurately locate on-site personnel, strengthen construction supervision, realize visual construction management, conduct in-process operations during construction, and in-depth control of potential safety hazards, timely feedback information, and effectively solve various construction difficulties.

2.5. Statistics of Road and Bridge Engineering volume

Although engineering cost estimates and data for roads and bridges must be accurate, the conventional working techniques used in the past were primarily manual computations, which not only took a lot of time but also had poor accuracy. Additionally, it will be challenging to communicate data and information if several specialists collaborate. The engineering quantity and cost of each construction link can be determined quickly and accurately by using BIM technology, and the data can not only be stored on the information platform to support the next construction link but can also be reviewed and consulted whenever necessary. The engineering quantity data gathered by BIM technology may be used to create building plans with a scientific and logical foundation in addition to calculating the cost of the bridge.

2.6. Coordinating Road and Bridge Construction projects

Many projects are involved in road and bridge engineering, and an essential component of management is the organization and coordination of multiple construction projects, which can speed up the project's construction process. Road and bridge building sites are small and lengthy, and there are sometimes many projects going on at the same time, affecting the bridge's construction quality and posing specific safety issues. The construction process may be replicated using BIM technology. According to research, completing the coordination of multiple projects prior to project construction will not only assure the project's construction quality, but also effectively optimize the construction schedule and decrease the probability of safety incidents on the construction site.

2.7. Road and Bridge Construction Schedule Management

The historical experience of road and bridge building schedule management demonstrates that there is a significant discrepancy between the actual timetable and the road and bridge construction plan. This is mostly owing to the unrealistic timetable management plan developed by management staff, as well as the inadequate sharing of construction schedule management data. By evaluating the virtual construction conflicts in the 4D model, the use of BIM technology in road and bridge construction management may generate a 4D virtual model and devise targeted solutions and management measures. At the construction site, the entry time of construction employees, supplies, and equipment, as well as the start and conclusion time of each project, should be precisely managed. To avoid project rework, the building process must be closely monitored and managed, and it is strictly banned to delay or waste time throughout the construction process.

2.8. Construction Equipment, Materials and Personnel Management

Road and bridge construction projects are extremely complex, requiring a large amount of equipment, construction employees, and building materials. If there are issues in some areas, such as equipment failure, a shortage of construction people, insufficient building supplies, and so on, it will make on-site management personnel's job more difficult and impede the smooth development of road and bridge projects. Managers can use the 4D model and information platform to understand the specific conditions of the equipment, materials, and personnel required at the construction site in advance, and formulate effective solutions, by applying BIM technology to road and bridge construction management.

2.9. Collaborative Design and Comprehensive Design of Pipelines

BIM requires the designer to attach building component attribute information to the model and show the collaborative design in a three-dimensional model. The program will create the relevant flat profile view when the model is produced and use the MEP plug-in in the same model. A 3D model of the structure and pipeline may be created using the piping system's layout as a guide. The prior technique involved superimposing the plans and adjusting the pipeline

junctions since there are several pipes and pieces of equipment set up in the utility tunnel. This procedure, which is frequently prone to mistakes, has significant requirements for the technicians' capacity to work in three dimensions and their mastery of varied professional information. Each major is modelled and integrated into the same central platform when BIM is used for pipeline design, and collision detection of components in the integrated body can quickly locate the point and make reasonable adjustments, which will increase work efficiency, facilitate professional coordination and cooperation, and reduce construction costs.

2.10. Quantity in Statistical Engineering

At the moment, most measuring and pricing software on the market, such as Guanglianda, Swell, and Luban, are based on two-dimensional drawings, which wastes time and personnel and is prone to mistakes. Furthermore, it is unavoidable that the employer will modify the design of the site while it is being built. Traditional modelling software cannot synchronously update to the change information, whereas BIM software can send the change information on time. Following the completion of the update, the engineering quantity is automatically calculated, and the table summary gives trustworthy data information for the cost budget and final account settlement.

2.11. Construction timeline and Process simulation

The building of an urban utility tunnel is an ever-changing process. The building time may be delayed due to climate factors, geological circumstances, and so on, so understanding the construction schedule is critical. Traditional software cannot graphically illustrate the project's timetable. BIM modelling, on the other hand, may connect the 3D model and time schedule to display the simulation run of the 4D construction timetable. The contact between the construction process and the team is carefully coordinated throughout the utility tunnel building, which is important job for the smooth construction. As a result, the use of BIM technology can dynamically monitor the project's difficult-to-solve challenges and pick the best solution.

2.12. 4D Virtual Construction

To add a temporal dimension to the 3D geometric space model and determine the real construction process, one can utilize a virtual simulation environment such as Autodesk Navis-works to perform 4D virtual construction. The construction organization timetable and progress-driven virtual simulation of the model are specifically linked to the BIM model. The following specific technical approaches are used: Autodesk Revit to create a 3D digital model using the parameters of each component's construction process, project preparation task data source, Navis-works integration model, and virtual model construction in a virtual environment. Real-time process interaction, virtual deduction construction programs, dynamic inspection programs, optimization and alterations to construction equipment, and technology are all concurrently discussed.

2.13. Program and Method of visualization of the submitted

Traditional two-dimensional CAD drawings, in order to represent engineering structural node design properly, frequently require the planning of a mix of many profiles. However, based on the three-dimensional digital model, BIM truly expresses the spatial geometry, position, and function of the engineering structure's nodes, makes complex space design more intuitive, realizes the model's "what you see is what you get," and can perform 360 degrees. Visualization of the visual aspect lowers construction workers' difficulties in comprehending drawings and successfully eliminates construction mistakes caused by drawing misinterpretation.

The three-dimensional presentation of construction node construction technique is used with BIM virtual simulation technology, and the structural design and construction scheme become more intuitive, making it easier for construction workers to grasp and apply. The model is imported into Autodesk Navis-works software and a virtual simulation environment is set up to show the model's construction methods for visualization after being created with Autodesk Revit software and defining the "stage" construction sequence of components.

2.14. Engineering Dynamic Accounting

In the building process, the engineering quantity is highly complicated, redundant, and wastes a big amount of labour and material force, and the accuracy is typically not well, has a large effect on the engineering measurement. The BIM digital information model, on the other hand, has an exact three-dimensional volume and building progress, allowing it to swiftly acquire the stage engineering amount. The particular procedure is as follows: Create a partial project BIM model in Revit and include body weight and construction stage attribute information for each model component. Count the current construction stage sub-item model body weight list according to the current construction state; Refer to the engineering formula rule for dimension formula calculation and create a portion of the project quantities from the model volume.

3. Implementation Process

3.1. Model Creation

To build a 3D topographic map, the project's terrain is recorded using UAV aerial photographs, the lidar is used to scan the terrain data to create a 3D terrain surface, and the real 3D terrain environment is integrated with satellite remote sensing images.

3.2. The Formation of the Geological Model

Creating the geological surface using the geological section: To design a road route and turn it into a three-dimensional characteristic line in Civil3D, the geological section is used as the longitudinal curve of the path, and the flat curve of the geological section is used as the flat curve of the path. Correction of drill pile data's geological surface. The drilling data is converted into a set of points that correspond to each geological surface. The geological surface is constructed by extracting each layer's 3D characteristic line and matching dot group file, as well as the two neighbouring components. The curving surfaces centre is a three-dimensional geological model.

The geological model application is based on the grade of surrounding rock and other geological circumstances as the judgment foundation to automatically identify the risk level, and different colours are utilized in the model to indicate the danger level of the construction interval. To accomplish the warning impact of geological changes, the step value is present in the BIM model, the distance between the pre-lithology change is within the range of the present step value, and the pre-lithology change data is communicated to the person in charge in the form of icons.

3.3. Construction of BIM model for Tunnel Construction

Object-oriented BIM model component library of tunnel construction is produced in accordance with the design, construction technique, process, and other aspects of composite lining tunnel construction by railroad mining law. The so-called object-oriented modelling approach, which divides the many components into groups based on how they relate to one another in the tunnel structure, defines the spatial shape and information properties of the components, and then puts them all together to create the model. Six main categories may be used to categorize the elements of the BIM model for composite lining tunnels: advance support, initial support, secondary lining, inverted arch filling, drainage prevention, and groove.

3.4. The creation of Component Repositories for BIM modelling

The four basic components of the definition of a component are component name, component coding, modelling accuracy, and information granularity, where the latter comprises both geometric and non-geometric information. Each component in the tunnel construction BIM model should have modelling accuracy that satisfies the following construction process management standards. Component units for advance tiny catheters, pipe sheds, hollow bolts, and mortar bolts should have the form of rings, with the adjacent two rings arranged in a plum-like pattern; steel mesh, steel frame, grille steel frame unit, which need to be in the form of a ring; The unit of shot crete should correspond to the longitudinal length of the excavation step since there is a significant variance in the surrounding rock levels, often 0.5 to 3.5 meters; Filling, flooring, inverted arch, and waterproofing unit component units should adhere to the mould-building length, which is typically 6 to 8 meters; Arch wall unit, should be moulded with a 10- to 12-meter longitudinal length.

4. Main problems in Construction of Road and Bridge

Road and bridge construction might confront a variety of problems, including:

- 4.1. **Budget and financing:** Adequate financing is required for building projects, and budget limits can cause delays or quality sacrifices.
- 4.2. **Environmental Concerns:** Projects must undergo environmental evaluations and follow rules to minimize their environmental impact.
- 4.3. **Land Acquisition:** Purchasing land for development can be a time-consuming and complicated procedure involving discussions and possibly legal issues.
- 4.4. **Design Challenges:** Complex engineering and architectural designs for bridges and roadways may be required, necessitating specialized skills.
- 4.5. **Weather Conditions:** Inclement weather can interrupt construction schedules and jeopardize worker safety.
- 4.6. **Material Availability:** The availability of construction materials can be a problem, particularly for remote sites.
- 4.7. **Safety Standards:** Maintaining worker safety and following to safety standards is critical, but it can be difficult on construction sites.
- 4.8. **Traffic Management:** Managing traffic during construction can be difficult, necessitating detours or temporary road closures.
- 4.9. **Regulatory Approvals:** Obtaining permissions and approvals from regulatory bodies might take time.
- 4.10. **Geotechnical Issues:** Unexpected problems can be posed by soil conditions, rock formations, and terrain.
- 4.11. **Quality Control:** It is vital for safety and longevity to maintain the quality and durability of infrastructure.
- 4.12. **Project Management:** Effective project management is required to coordinate multiple tasks, contractors, and schedules.

5. Main problems in Construction of Utility Tunnels

5.1. Imperfect Construction Standards

The building of the utility tunnel was earlier began in Germany, France, Japan, and other nations. Paris started constructing subterranean utility tunnels as early as 1832. China's national circumstances differ from those in other countries. We cannot slavishly copy the urban planning practices of other nations. Additionally, China's economic situation does not permit the large-scale engineering of utility tunnels beneath the earth. China therefore started later than expected, its rules and regulations were not sufficiently specific, and its management structure for projects involving utility tunnels was also not ideal [17]. The "Technical code for urban utility tunnel engineering" (GB50838-2015) makes it clear that the circular section of the shield in the construction method is not clearly defined, and the requirements and regulations for the cable duct are not sufficiently detailed. This makes it impossible to have a basis for the design and construction of utility tunnels.

5.2. Large Investment Cost

Due to several factors, including the high cost and difficult operation and maintenance at a later time, the utility tunnel construction must be designed as a complete. Consider the Liupanshui utility tunnel as an example. Its cost is around 80 million per km, whereas the cost of civil engineering is approximately 45 to 50 million per kilo meter. The government still isn't able to support the extensive advertising and building since the project unit's cost is so expensive. The government has actively promoted the PPP model to encourage investment in utility tunnel development since 2014. The promotion of this model hasn't gained much traction yet, state-supported policies aren't specific enough, and investors are wary of making irrational bets, so the construction of the municipal utility tunnel can only rely on government funding and a lack of private sector investment.

5.3. Difficult Construction and Coordination

The building of the urban utility tunnel will be delayed by a number of unanticipated events, including difficult geological conditions, conflicts with the old municipal pipes, issues with how the pipelines enter the ditch, and so forth. In addition, issues with building might arise from a shortage of qualified engineers and technicians. Most cities have not yet built an efficient communication and coordination mechanism among pipeline ownership entities since the management system has not yet been fully developed. As a result, it is challenging to come to a consensus over cost-sharing for building, operation and maintenance, etc., which further impedes the progress of the tunnel.

6. Software Configuration

Modelling software like as Revit and Civil3D are commonly used, and the implementation process is mostly based on the BIM5D platform.

Table 1: Summary table of the Software

Number	Software Brand	Software Version	Function & Application
1	Revit	2018	Construction and Maintenance of civil engineering, site layout, electromechanical models, data entry and export, etc.
2	Navisworks	2018	Used for the summary and examination of various professional models, pipeline collision detection, three-dimensional roaming, disclosure, etc.
3	Civil 3D	2018	Construction of terrain and geological models, export of spatial coordinates and other data, etc.
4	Dynamo	2.0.1	Graphical platform for secondary development, script development for improving workflow, and construction of tunnel and pipeline relocation models
5	Lumion	6	Video rendering and production
6	BIM 5D	The Latest edition Of the 2017	Application of quality, safety, schedule and cost after integrating the model
7	XZglodon	The Latest edition Of the 2017	Data storage and cloud-based applications
8	Construction site Of Intelligentization	/	Refined, informatized, and scientifically managed first-line production on construction site

Conclusion

Information management models are more effective than present management approaches in enhancing the intensity and efficacy of management while developing roads and bridges. In addition to improving project safety management efficiency, BIM technology can be used to establish scientific and effective project management. For road and bridge projects to be safe and run smoothly, managers must implement information-based risk detection methods and produce precise construction plans.

It is clear that the use of BIM technology in road and bridge engineering construction management plays an essential role in road bridge building, which may support roads and bridges to achieve good economic and social advantages. Managers can make better decisions with BIM, create a true and reliable foundation, scientifically manage the entire road and bridge construction process, reduce construction costs, avoid quality and safety accidents, and guarantee completion time. BIM technology, as a result, should be widely implemented in future road and bridge construction management to encourage the fast expansion of transportation networks.

The utility tunnel construction process uses BIM technology, which allows for the collision detection of 3D models, avoids the information incompatibility of traditional design modes, enhances the coordination effectiveness of various departments, and reduces time and cost for project construction. These advantages are maximized. Additionally, it facilitates construction management, construction technology optimization, progress control, and visual technical disclosure, giving assurance for the caliber of underground utility tunnel construction. Engineering construction is moving in a new direction thanks to BIM technology. Urban utility tunnel construction using BIM technology overcomes the technical limitations of conventional pipeline construction, identifies impending design and construction issues in advance, enhances construction quality and efficiency, and lowers construction and operation costs. Additionally, the model data is given to the management unit in charge of operations and maintenance in order to raise the utility tunnel's maintenance standard. This will serve as a guide and technical support for achieving the informationalisation and intellectualization of underground utility tunnel construction, operation, and maintenance.

The use of BIM technology in tunnel engineering is only in the exploring phase at the moment. BIM model of tunnel composite lining construction is established by using the three-dimensional modelling method oriented to engineering entity objects, which can help with 4D Virtual Construction Management and 3D Visual Design of tunnel construction organization, in accordance with the structural nomenclature of construction components and the precision requirements of process management. Based on BIM visual simulation technology, the method and procedure for automatically calculating the project volume are established, along with the 3D model visualization design of tunnel construction technology scheme, the 4D model virtual construction deduction, and optimization of tunnel construction scheme.

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